

FAILURE ANALYSIS ON VARIABLE THICKNESS COMPOSITE BEAMS UNDER 4-P TEST BENDING

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ABSTRACT

If the design of a laminated composite beam accounts for the concept of variable thickness, a remarkable weight saving can be obtained. In the present work, a theoretical study dealing with the stress distributions in tapered composite beams is presented. A finite element model has been used for calculating the stress components.

A four point bending model has been applied. Three types of composite materials are analyzed: Graphite/epoxy, Aramide/epoxy and Fiberglass/epoxy. Influence of material, laminate thickness, geometry, bending moment and aspect ratio on through-thickness stress distributions are studied.

KEYWORDS: Interlaminar Stresses; Shear; Bending Tests.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have been increasingly used during the last decades, in order to light structures in fields like aeronautics and space. Two steps are essential in the process of taking advantage of this kind of materials: design and optimization.

In order to solve the problem of optimizing a composite structure, the variable thickness effect must be studied and understood properly.

Ochoa and Chan (1) reported an outstanding work on delamination of tapered laminated subjected to in-plane loads. Quite a few references of failure modes in tapered laminates subjected to transverse loads have been found. All of them deal with applications to specific pieces (2) to (4). Recently, Kim and Miravete (5) studied the failure mechanisms of tapered laminated composite plates.

In the present work, a study of the stress distributions of variable thickness composite beams subjected to transverse loads is presented. A theoretical model based on a plane strain finite element theory is described.

2. MODEL ASSUMPTIONS AND METHOD OF ANALYSIS

The model used here presents the following assumptions:

- This study is limited to one-dimensional laminated composite plates, in order to avoid three-dimensional effects and to analyze properly the consequences of the variable thickness effect.
- The fiber orientation is longitudinal (x-direction). This is the optimal direction for one-dimensional laminated composite plates.
- A 2-D plane strain finite element model has been used.
- The mesh is composed by 1891 nodes.
- A three point bending model has been used for analyzing the failure mechanisms (5) and mechanical behavior (6) of tapered composite beams. However, a four point bending model seems more adequate for stress distribution studies because bending moment is constant and shear force vanishes at the middle of the span for constant thickness beams. Thus, for a tapered beam, interlaminar stress distributions in this area will be generated only by variable thickness effects.
- Three materials have been used: Graphite/epoxy AS4/3501, Kevlar 39/epoxy and Glass E/epoxy. Mechanical properties are given in Table 1.

3. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The definition of variables is shown in Figure 1. A 4 point bending model has been applied for the three types of materials mentioned above.

This study is focussed upon the interlaminar shear (σ_5) distribution because it is the critical component in this model. Experimental results show delamination failure modes in the tapered area. The peak of σ_5 (σ_{5max}) is the critical parameter in the generation of this delamination.

This value (σ_{5max}) is function of the material and the ratio (t_1/t). Figure 2 shows the variation of σ_{5max} with respect to these two parameters. On the one hand, Fiberglass E/epoxy presents the maximum value and graphite/epoxy the minimum. On the other hand, variation of σ_{5max} in function of t_1/t presents a maximum, that is function of the material.

σ_{5max} is proportional to the bending moment at the middle of the span $P(L-L_1)/2$ (Figures 3 to 6). And finally, σ_{5max} is not a function of the aspect ratio (L/t).

4. CONCLUSIONS

The variable thickness effect in tapered laminated composite beams has been analyzed. A numerical modeling based on a plain strain finite element model and a 4-point bending model has been carried out.

Distributions of interlaminar shear stress (σ_5) distributions through thickness in the tapered area of a composite beam have been presented.

The influence of some parameters over the peak of the distribution of σ_5 has been analyzed in this study.

These three conclusions can be drawn:

- σ_{5max} is a function of the material, fiberglass E/epoxy presenting the maximum value and graphite/epoxy the minimum.
- σ_{5max} is a function of the bending moment. A linear relationship between the interlaminar shear stress distribution and the bending moment has been found.
- σ_{5max} is a function of the ratio t_1/t . As can be seen in Figure 2. There is no linearity in the relationship between this parameter and the interlaminar shear stress distribution. A maximum value can be found in the range of between 1.2 and 1.4.

TABLE 1. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Material	AS4/3501	Kev39/epoxy	E Glass/epoxy
Ex (GPa)	138.00	76.00	38.60
Ey (GPa)	8.96	5.50	8.27
vx	0.30	0.34	0.26
Es (GPa)	7.10	2.30	4.14
Vf	0.66	0.60	0.45

5. REFERENCES

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FIGURE 1. Definition of variables.

FIGURE 2. Distribution of $\sigma_{5 \max}$ in function of t_1/t .

Distribution of interlaminar shear stresses for AS4/3501.

$$P=1E5 \text{ N/m.}$$

FIGURE 3. Definition of the geometry.

Distribution of interlaminar shear stresses for AS4/3501.

FIGURE 4. Distribution of interlaminar shear stress for the specimen defined in Figure 3.

Distribution of interlaminar shear stresses for AS4/3501.

$$P = 1E5 \text{ N/m.}$$

FIGURE 5. Definition of the geometry.

Distribution of interlaminar shear stresses for AS4/3501.

FIGURE 6. Distribution of interlaminar shear stress for the specimen defined in Figure 5.